

S-SUBSTITUTED THIOUREAS AS ANALYTICAL REAGENTS. PART III.
S-METHYLTHIOUREA SULPHATE AS A COLORIMETRIC
REAGENT FOR NICKEL AND COBALT

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S-Methylthiourea sulphate has been employed as a colorimetric reagent for cobalt and nickel in ammoniacal medium. The colour formed is deep enough to make the reagent sensitive. Beer's law is obeyed. The effects of variation of the ageing period, the pH of the medium and the amount of the reagent have been studied, and suitable filters, indicated.

Applications of substituted thioureas in chemical analysis are few, and the only studies in this line appear to be those of Steiger (*Microchem.*, 1934-35, 16, 193) and of Yoe and Overholser (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1942, 14, 435). These studies are mainly qualitative and limited to the determination of sensitiveness of colour reactions of a large number of substituted thioureas with many metallic ions. Siddhanta and Kundu (Part I, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 655) have found that nickel and copper can be estimated gravimetrically as their mercaptides by precipitating the latter from their alkaline solutions with S-methylthiourea sulphate. In Part II, Siddhanta and Banerjee (*ibid.*, 1958, 35, 53) have successfully employed the same reagent for gravimetric estimation of silver. In the present work it has been found that cobalt also forms precipitate of deep brown cobalt methylmercaptide by adding a solution of S-methylthiourea sulphate to a hot alkaline solution of cobalt salt. The precipitate, however, reaches stoichiometric composition, $Co(CH_3S)_2$, only when the reagent added is less than the required amount. But with an excess of the reagent, the cobalt mercaptide precipitate becomes contaminated with oily oxidation products of methylmercaptide, thus restricting its use as a gravimetric reagent for cobalt.

However, the reagent could form coloured stable colloidal solutions with very dilute solutions of nickel and cobalt salts. Such colloidal solutions obey Beer's law and, hence, both cobalt and nickel can be estimated colorimetrically. The estimations were made with a Duboscq colorimeter, using standard solutions of cobalt and nickel for comparison. The filter chosen was 495 $m\mu$ for cobalt and 495 $m\mu$ to 510 $m\mu$ for nickel, as indicated by the maximum optical density in

a Leifo photometer. The best result for cobalt was obtained with 180 times excess of the reagent, between p_H range 8.75 and 9.70, with cobalt concentration varying from 0.5 to 7.0 γ /c.c. and that for nickel with 40-fold excess of the reagent, between p_H range 9.14 and 9.51, with nickel concentration varying from 1.0 to 7.0 γ /c.c. The ageing period in case of cobalt is two hours, and that for nickel is one hour. The detection limit for cobalt is 0.17 γ /c.c. and that for nickel is 0.45 γ /c.c.

EXPERIMENTAL

Cobalt methylmercaptide appears not to have been described in earlier literature. It is prepared as a brown precipitate by mixing solutions of cobalt nitrate and S-methylthiourea sulphate (molar ratio, 1:2) in ammoniacal medium at about 60°. [Found: Co(as sulphate), 38.63; S(as sulphate by peroxide fusion), 41.04. Calc. for $\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{S})_2$: Co, 38.55; S, 41.84%). Nickel methylmercaptide, $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{S})_2$ has been prepared by Siddhanta and Kundu (*loc. cit.*). Stock solutions of cobalt and nickel were prepared with cobalt nitrate (B.D.H.-AnalaR, Ni, 0.01%) and nickel sulphate (Hopkin and Williams Ltd., AnalaR, Co, 0.0005%) and estimated by the usual procedure. S-Methylthiourea sulphate (B.D.H., Lab. Reagent) solution, once prepared, could be kept for a few days without decomposition. All dilutions were made with bidistilled water on each day of the experiment from respective stock solutions. The p_H determinations were made with a Beckman p_H -meter (model H-2).

FIG. 1

Values of the extinction coefficient for nickel and cobalt solutions observed with different filters are represented in Fig. 1. The optimum time for keeping the solution mixtures before colorimetric comparison was determined from the horizontal portion of the plot of extinction coefficient against time, using different dilutions of cobalt (5.0, 2.5 and 0.57 γ /c.c.) and nickel (7.57, 1.07 γ /c.c.) solutions (vide Fig. 2).

TABLE I
Verification of Beer's law.

1st. Soln.					2nd. Soln.				
Reagent soln. (i) 7 c.c. (0.0284 g. c.c.).					(ii) 2 c.c. (0.01422 g. c.c.).				
Ammonia soln. (i) 3 c.c. of 0.151 N.					(ii) 3 c.c. of 0.1409 N				
Total volume (i) 20 c.c.					(ii) 20 c.c.				
Ageing period (i) 2 hours.					(ii) 1 hour.				
Cobalt solution (0.001%)					Cobalt solution (0.001%)				
1st. soln.		2nd. soln.		% Diff.	1st. soln.		2nd. soln.		% Diff.
Vol.	Length.	Vol.	Length.		Vol.	Length.	Vol.	Length.	
*10 c.c.	12.0 mm	3 c.c.	39.98 mm	0.05	13 c.c.	24.83 mm	8 c.c.	40 mm	0.9
9	15.2	3	45.0	1.4	12	20.66	8	30	3.3
*6	20.0	3	40.2	0.5	3	30.2	*2	45	0.7
7	19.2	3	45	0.5	8	22.7	6	30	1.0
4	20.1	2	41	0.5	10	24.0	8	30	0.0
9	22.3	5	40	0.5	9	25.0	7	32	0.4
14	20.3	8	35	1.5	9	25.0	*8	28.6	1.6
Cobalt soln. (0.001%).					Nickel soln. (0.001%).				
3	41.4	5	25	0.75	14	10	4	35.30	0.80
4	39.2	8	20	2.00	4	20	2	40.63	1.57
1	40.0	*2	20.2	1.00	8	20	4	40.18	0.48
4	38.9	10	16	2.75	10	18	6	30.00	0.30
2	45.2	6	15	0.40	15	40	14	39.02	0.80
1	39.3	0.8	40	18.20	6	30	8	22.44	0.25
0.8	18.2	0.4	40	9.00	10	35	15	24.20	3.72
					6	40	12	20.10	0.48

* Solutions having an ageing period of six hours.

N.B. It has been observed in the case of cobalt that if the solution in one limb is exposed to air during the ageing period, while that in the other limb is not exposed, the readings differ by a large amount. If, now, the unexposed solution is exposed for some time to air and the readings are again taken, then the error comes within the usual limit. So there is some relation between intensity of colour formation and exposure to air in this case.

Effect of Variation of Ammonia and Reagent in Cobalt Estimation

The results of comparison of colour, developed in two solutions side by side, as done in a Duboscq colorimeter, have been shown in Table II. The first solution contained in every case 5 c.c. of 0.001% cobalt solution, 2 c.c. of the reagent solution (0.01422 g./c.c.), 3 c.c. of ammonia solution (0.151 N) and sufficient water to make the total volume 20 c.c., giving a p_{21} value of 9.12 (a p_{21} at which Beer's law is obeyed). The second solution contained in every case, 5 c.c. of the same cobalt solution, 2 c.c. of the same reagent solution, varying volumes of ammonia and enough water to make the total volume 20 c.c., for studying the effect of the variation of ammonia (top left of Table II, columns 1, 2 and 3; the

lengths of the second solution required to match 30 mm of the first solutions have been shown in column 3). In order to study the effect of reagent variation, both the solutions always contained 5 c.c. of cobalt solutions (0.001%), varying volumes of the reagent and 3 c.c. of 0.151N ammonia solution, whereby p_H values varied from 8.95 to 9.20 for the 'first' solution and from 8.95 to 9.32 for the 'second' solutions. The results have been shown in columns 4, 5 and 6 (top right, Table II). The effect of simultaneous variation of cobalt and the reagent has been shown in columns 4, 5 and 6 (bottom right, Table II). In this case also, both the first and second solutions were made up to 20 c.c. after mixing up the cobalt, reagent and ammonia solutions. In each case an ageing period of $2\frac{1}{2}$ to 3 hours was allowed before the comparison of colour was made.

FIG. 2

I: 510 m μ , 1.0 γ /c.c. Ni.	VI: 495 m μ , 2.5 γ /c.c. Co.
II: 495 " " " "	VII: 510 " 5.0 " "
III: 510 " 0.5 " Co.	VIII: 495 " 5.0 " "
IV: 495 " " " "	IX: 510 " 7.5 " Ni.
V: 510 " 2.5 " "	X: 495 " " " "

TABLE II

Cobalt soln. = 4 c.c. of .001%. Total vol. = 20 c.c. Ageing time = 2½ to 3 hours.

Vol. of NH ₄ OH (0.15N) in 2nd. soln.	p _H (2nd. soln.)	Length (2nd. soln. against 30 mm of 1st. soln.).	Vol. of reagent soln. (0.01422 g./c.c.) in		Length (2nd. soln., against 30 mm- of 1st. soln.).
Variation of ammonia.			1st. soln.	2nd. soln.	Variation of reagent.
0.5 c.c.	8.60	32.88 mm	2.0 c.c.	1.0 c.c.	40.50 mm
1.0	8.75	29.80	4.0	2.5	32.50
1.5	8.87	30.10	3.0	2.0	34.07
2.0	9.00	29.83	3.5	2.5	32.45
4.0	9.21	30.66	2.0	1.5	35.37
6.0	9.35	30.32	4.0	3.0	30.23
7.0	9.42	29.50	3.0	3.5	29.70
8.0	9.53	29.77	3.0	4.0	29.30
10.0	9.68	30.33	Simultaneous variation of cobalt and reagent.		
12.0	9.69	29.80	*6	7	*30.1
13.0	9.72	31.13	*6	8	*29.7
			≠6	7	≠29.9
			≠6	8	≠29.2
Signs * and ≠ correspond to 4 c.c. of 0.001% and 8 c.c. of 0.001% cobalt solns. respectively.			*6	6	≠15.3
			*7	7	≠15.1
In these cases other conditions are : ammonia solution, 3 c.c. of 0.15N; ageing time, 2 hours;			*8	8	≠15.2
reagent conc., 0.0284 g./c.c., and total volume, 20 c.c.			*6	7	≠15.4
			*7	8	≠15.0
			*6	8	≠14.5

It may be observed from the above table, that for cobalt estimation the reaction is incomplete below p_H 8.75. There is, however, a tendency for the precipitate to coagulate above p_H 9.70. The minimum reagent to be added in the estimation of cobalt is about 180 times the amount theoretically required.

Effect of Variation of Ammonia and Reagent in Nickel Estimation

From Table III it is observed that the optimum p_H range for nickel estimation is between 9.14 and 9.51 and the minimum amount of the reagent to be used is 40 times the theoretically required value.

TABLE III

Ni soln. = 10 c.c. of 0.001%. Total vol. = 20 c.c. Ageing time = $\frac{1}{2}$ hour.
(Length of first solution for matching = 30 mm).

First solution.			Second solution.			
Volume added of		μ_n .	Volume added of		Length (against 30 mm. of 1st. soln.).	μ_n .
Ammonia (0.1409N).	Reagent soln. (0.01422 g./c.c.).		Ammonia (0.1409N).	Reagent solu. (0.01422 g./c.c.).		
Variation of ammonia						
3 c.c.	2 c.c.	9.30	1 c.c.	2 c.c.	No. match possible.	8.99
3	"	9.30	2	"	29.13 mm.	9.14
4	"	9.45	3	"	30.10	9.30
4	"	9.45	4	"	30.17	9.45
3	"	9.30	3	"	29.62	9.30
2	"	9.15	2	"	29.80	9.14
Variation of the reagent.						
3	2.6	9.25	3	2.6	30.18	9.20
"	2.0	9.39	"	2.0	29.95	9.35
"	1.3	9.47	"	1.3	30.21	9.51
"	0.7	9.75	"	0.7	25.00	9.72
"	2.0	9.35	"	2.6	30.72	9.20
"	1.3	9.51	"	2.0	29.91	9.35
"	0.7	9.72	"	1.3	18.00	9.51
"	1.3	9.51	"	2.6	29.59	9.20

Mixtures of reagent solution, ammonia and either nickel or cobalt solution have been compared against blank solutions containing the reagent and ammonia under identical conditions in the Duboscq colorimeter, and the minimum concentration of the metal, below which the colour difference becomes imperceptible, has been found out.

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